

Evolution of Interoperability Standards

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report provides first a landscape on interoperability standards, focusing on

- ICT standards,
 - distributed systems,
 - cloud computing, and
 - internet of things and digital twin, and
- application domain standards,
 - health,
 - energy.

It then elaborates on the changing context concerning

- the complexity of ecosystems or socio-technical systems,
- the increasing number of policies and regulations, and
- the evolution of interoperability frameworks.

It then describes the expected evolution of standardisation practice for interoperability, consisting of moves towards

- the interoperability of standards,
- the interoperability of concepts and architectures across multiple standardization instances, and
- the interoperability of systems in complex ecosystems.

The report concludes with a call to anticipate a new ecosystem of standardisation practices.

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1 Introduction

The recent CrowdStrike outage¹ was a typical example of cascading effects. A routine security software update was initiated. Upon executing, the security software was instructed to read an entry that was out of memory, thus causing the operating system to crash². The effect of the update was seen very early on since the update was stopped within 80 minutes. Further the fix could be developed in a couple of hours, but its deployment took place about one week later. It can be claimed that this outage can also be seen as a failure of the interoperability assurance process, or of behavioral interoperability: while the software update function was operational, the effect of the software update was not well tested.

This report provides an analysis on the evolution of interoperability standards and shows that it should or will evolve into directions to address the growing complexity of ICT infrastructure systems, or ICT ecosystems. The report first provides an overview on standards on interoperability, at the ICT level, at the domain level, as well as at the conformance assessment level. It then describes challenges they need to address in terms of ecosystems complexity, of policies and regulation constraints, and of interoperability frameworks. It finally provides an analysis on how some key standardisation undertakings can be leveraged and combined to address these challenges:

- standards to support the interoperability of standards,
- standards to support the interoperability of concepts and of architectures, and
- standards to support the assurance of interoperable systems.

Abbreviations

IEC International Electrotechnical Commission
IHE Integrating the Healthcare Enterprise
IoT Internet of Things
ISO International Organization for Standardization
ITU-T International Telecommunication Union Telecommunication Standardization Sector
JTC Joint Technical Committee
OSI Open Systems Interconnection
RFC Request for Comment
RM-ODP Reference Model of Open Distributed Processing
SC Sub Committee
TC Technical Committee
TCP/IP Transmission Control Protocol/Internet Protocol

¹ The computer outage of July 19, 2024 was caused by a faulty update of Falcon Sensor, software from the cybersecurity company CrowdStrike. This defective update caused the blocking of 8.5 million computers and servers worldwide. It was estimated in August 2023 that the outage will cost \$5.4 billion in damages to the 500 largest US companies (<https://fortune.com/2024/08/03/crowdstrike-outage-fortune-500-companies-5-4-billion-damages-uninsured-losses/>).

² See <https://www.crowdstrike.com/blog/falcon-content-update-preliminary-post-incident-report/> and <https://www.crowdstrike.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/Channel-File-291-Incident-Root-Cause-Analysis-08.06.2024.pdf>

2 Landscape on Interoperability Standards

2.1 ICT Standards

2.1.1 Distributed Systems

Interoperability concerns can be traced back to the days of computing network methods in the late 1970s with the creation of an interoperability framework based on the OSI model as exemplified by

- the joint work in the 1980s of ITU-T X.200 (open systems interconnection basic reference model) and ISO/IEC 7498-1, and
- the publication of internet protocol suite (TCP/IP) or RFC 1122

This was followed by architecture work on RM-ODP (Reference model for Open distributed processing), jointly published by ITU-T (X.901 to X 904) and ISO/IEC (ISO/IEC 10746 serie). RM-ODP consisted of 4 parts:

- an overview,
- foundations,
- architecture,
- architecture semantics.

The mentioned standards are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 – Examples of distributed systems standards (ITU-T, ISO/IEC, IETF)

Category	Title		Date	URL	
Interoperability framework	Open Systems Interconnection (OSI) Basic Reference Model	ITU-T X-200	1988, 1994	https://www.itu.int/rec/T-REC-X.200/	
		ISO/IEC 7498-1	1994	https://www.iso.org/standard/20269.html	
	Requirements for Internet Hosts -- Communication Layers	RFC 1122	1989	https://www.rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc1122	
Architecture	Open Distributed Processing (ODP) Reference Model	Overview	ITU-T X-901	1997	https://www.itu.int/rec/T-REC-X.901/en
			ISO/IEC 10746-1	1998	https://www.iso.org/standard/20696.html
		Foundations	ITU-T X-902	1995, 2009	https://www.itu.int/rec/T-REC-X.902/en
			ISO/IEC 10746-2	1996, 2009	https://www.iso.org/standard/55723.html
		Architecture	ITU-T X-903	1995, 2009	https://www.itu.int/rec/T-REC-X.903/en
			ISO/IEC 10746-3	1996, 2009	https://www.iso.org/standard/55724.html
		Architectural semantics	ITU-T X-904	1997	https://www.itu.int/rec/T-REC-X.903/en
ISO/IEC 10746-4	1998	https://www.iso.org/standard/20698.html			

2.1.2 Cloud Computing

Recently established subcommittees in JTC 1³ have followed the same pattern of standard categories to address high-level guidance on interoperability:

- standards on use cases, vocabulary, concepts;
- standards on architecture; and
- standards on an interoperability framework.

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38 (**Cloud computing and distributed platforms**) was established in 2009, with interoperability concerns relating to the networking of elements providing cloud services. The subcommittee

- started publishing standards on cloud vocabulary with ISO/IEC 17788 in 2014, later replaced by ISO/IEC Ed1 22123-1 in 2021, and 2023;

³ Information on the history of JTC1 subcommittees can be found in <https://jtc1info.org/sd-2-history/>

- started publishing standards on cloud architecture with ISO/IEC 17789 in 2014, later replaced by ISO/IEC 22123-3 in 2023; and then
- started publishing standards on cloud interoperability with ISO/IEC 19941 in 2017, to be replaced by a new edition under development.

Mentioned cloud computing standards are showed in Table 2.

Table 2 – Examples of cloud computing standards (ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38)

Category	Title	ISO/IEC	Date	URL
Use cases, vocabulary and concepts	Overview and vocabulary	ISO/IEC 17788	2014	https://www.iso.org/standard/60545.html
	Vocabulary	ISO/IEC 22123-1	2021, 2023	https://www.iso.org/standard/82759.html
	Concepts	ISO/IEC 22123-2	2021, 2023	https://www.iso.org/standard/80351.html
Architecture	Reference architecture	ISO/IEC 17789	2014	https://www.iso.org/standard/60545.html
		ISO/IEC 22123-3	2023	https://www.iso.org/standard/82759.html
Interoperability framework	Interoperability and portability	ISO/IEC 19941	2017, 2024	https://www.iso.org/standard/87817.html

2.1.3 Internet of Things and Digital Twin

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41 (**Internet of things and digital twin**), was established in 2016, initially focusing on the Internet of Things (IoT), and in 2020 on digital twins. IoT interoperability deals with the connectivity of cyber physical systems through sensors and actuators. Digital twin interoperability deals with the connectivity of digital twins with the physical entity. The subcommittee

- started publishing standards on IoT vocabulary with ISO/IEC 20924 in 2018, 2021, and in 2023 to cover both IoT and digital twins;
- started publishing standards on IoT architecture with the publication of ISO/IEC 30141 in 2018, later replaced by a second edition in 2024, the development of ISO/IEC 40141 as a guidance document, complemented by the publication of ISO/IEC 30147 and ISO/IEC 30149 on trustworthiness.
- started publishing standards on IoT interoperability with the publication of ISO/IEC 21823 series (IoT interoperability), with part 1 on the framework in 2019, part 2 on the transport facet in 2020, part 3 on the semantic facet in 2021, part 4 on the syntactic facet in 2022, and part 5 on the behavioural and policy facets (under development).

At this point there is no specific standard on digital twin interoperability. It is however addressed in ISO/IEC 30188 (Digital twin reference architecture) which is under development. Mentioned Internet of things standards are showed in Table 3.

Table 3 – Examples of internet of things standards (ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41)

Category	Title	ISO/IEC	Date	URL
Use cases, vocabulary and concepts	IoT Vocabulary	ISO/IEC 20924	2018, 2021	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/66217
	IoT and digital twin - Vocabulary	ISO/IEC 20924	2024	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/70408
Architecture	IoT Reference architecture	ISO/IEC 30141	2018, 2024	https://www.iso.org/standard/88800.html
	Digital twin reference architecture	ISO/IEC 30188	Development	https://www.iec.ch/dyn/www/f?p=103:38:411109607072878:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_APEX_PAGE,FSP_PROJECT_ID:20486,23,104896
	Guidance on reference architecture	ISO/IEC TR 40141	2024	https://www.iec.ch/ords/f?p=103:38:710954471973193:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_APEX_PAGE,FSP_PROJECT_ID:20486,23,126453
	IoT Trustworthiness Integration in ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288 system engineering processes	ISO/IEC 30147	2021	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/62644
	IoT Trustworthiness principles	ISO/IEC TS 30149	2024	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/67281
Interoperability framework	Framework	ISO/IEC 21823-1	2019	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/60604
	Transport interoperability	ISO/IEC 21823-2	2020	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/61085
	Semantic interoperability	ISO/IEC 21823-3	2021	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/61088
	Syntactic interoperability	ISO/IEC 21823-4	2022	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/65649
	Behavioural and policy interoperability	ISO/IEC 21823-5	Development	https://www.iec.ch/ords/f?p=103:38:604746112772042:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_APEX_PAGE,FSP_PROJECT_ID:20486,23,108353

2.2 Application Domain Standards

On the other hand, well established committees focusing on application domain standards further develop interoperability standards. We cover two application domains: health and energy.

2.2.1 Health

In the health domain, ISO TC 215 (**Health informatics**), established in 1998, addresses the interchange and use of health-related data:

- standards on architecture with the publication of the ISO 12967 series on service architecture in 2009, updated and 2020, with part 1 on the enterprise viewpoint, part 2 on the information viewpoint and part 3 on the computational viewpoint; this was followed by the publication in 2021 of ISO 23903 on an interoperability and integration reference architecture;
- standards on interoperability protocols with the publication of HL7 version 2 message system in 1987, the publication of HL7 version 3 message system in 2011, and the publication of HL7 FHIR in 2011;
- standards on information models, with the publication of the reference information model (RIM) in 1996, with ISO/HL7 21731 in 2006 and 2014, the publication of the HL7 clinical document architecture, with ISO/HL7 27932 in 2009, and the publication of ISO 13972 in 2022 on clinical information models; further, the publication in 2014 of the ISO 13606 series on electronic health record communication, with part 1 on a reference model, part 2 on archetype interchange specification, part 3 on archetypes and term list, part 4 on security and part 5 on interface specifications;
- standards on interoperability frameworks, with the publication of the ISO 22600 series in 2014 on privilege management and access control, with part 1 on overview and policy management, part 2 on formal models and part 3 on implementations, and
- standards on interoperability profiles based on the work from IHE⁴, with the publication in 2014 of the ISO 28380 series list protocol standards, with part 1 on the process, part 2 on integration and content profiles and part 3 on deployment.

Mentioned health standards are showed in Table 4. Note that the rate of evolution on information can be huge in health, considering for instance the WHO international classification of diseases⁵, so it is likely that a wealth of new standards will be provided in the future.

Table 4 – Examples of health informatics standards (HL7, ISO TC215)

Category	Title	Date	URL		
Architecture	Health informatics — Service architecture (HISA)	Enterprise viewpoint	ISO 12967-1	2009, 2020	https://www.iso.org/standard/71037.html
		Information viewpoint	ISO 12967-2	2009, 2020	https://www.iso.org/standard/71038.html
		Computational viewpoint	ISO 12967-3	2009, 2020	https://www.iso.org/standard/71039.html
	Interoperability and integration reference architecture — Model and framework	ISO TR 23903	2021	https://www.iso.org/standard/77337.html	
Interoperability protocol	HL7 Version 2 Product Suite		1987-2011	https://www.hl7.org/implement/standards/product_brief.cfm?product_id=185	
	HL7 Version 3 Product Suite		2011 - 2014	https://www.hl7.org/implement/standards/product_brief.cfm?product_id=186	
	HL7 Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR)		2011 - 2023	https://hl7.org/fhir/directory.html	
Information Model	HL7 Version 3 — Reference Information Model (RIM)		1996 - 2021	https://www.hl7.org/implement/standards/rim.cfm	
	HL7 version 3 — Reference information model — Release 4	ISO/HL7 21731	2006, 2014	https://www.iso.org/standard/61454.html	
	HL7 Clinical Document Architecture		2000, 2005	https://www.hl7.org/implement/standards/product_brief.cfm?product_id=7	

⁴ <https://www.ihe.net/>

⁵ <https://icd.who.int/en>

	Data Exchange Standards — HL7 Clinical Document Architecture, Release 2		ISO/HL7 27932	2009	https://www.iso.org/standard/44429.html
	Clinical information models — Characteristics, structures and requirements		ISO 13972	2022	https://www.iso.org/standard/79498.html
	Electronic health record communication	Reference model	ISO 13606-1	2008, 2019	https://www.iso.org/standard/67868.html
		Archetype interchange specification	ISO 13606-2	2008, 2019	https://www.iso.org/standard/62305.html
		Reference archetypes and term lists	ISO 13606-3	2009, 2019	https://www.iso.org/standard/62303.html
		Security	ISO 13606-4	2009, 2019	https://www.iso.org/standard/62306.html
	Interface specification	ISO 13606-5	2010, 2019	https://www.iso.org/standard/62304.html	
Interoperability framework	Privilege management and access control	Overview and policy management	ISO 22600-1	2014	https://www.iso.org/standard/62653.html
		Formal models	ISO 22600-2	2014	https://www.iso.org/standard/62654.html
		Implementations	ISO 22600-3	2014	https://www.iso.org/standard/62655.html
Interoperability profile	IHE global standards adoption	Process	ISO TR 28380-1	2014	https://www.iso.org/standard/63383.html
		Integration and content profiles	ISO TR 28380-2	2014	https://www.iso.org/standard/46207.html
		Deployment	ISO TR 28380-3	2014	https://www.iso.org/standard/61471.html

2.2.2 Energy

In the energy domain, IEC committees such as SyC Smart Energy and TC57 (**Power systems management and associated information exchange**), address architecture, interoperability, information models and ontologies, or interoperability profiles:

- Standards on architecture with the publication of the smart grid architecture model and associated interoperability framework by the CEN-CENELEC-ETSI SG-CG (smart grid coordination group) in 2012/2016 and transposed into an international System Reference Deliverable with IEC SRD 63200 in 2021
- Standards on interoperability with the publication in 2004 of the IEC 61850 standard series in the power utility automation domain⁶, e.g., IEC TR 61850-1 in 2017, IEC 61850-5 in 2013, or IEC 61850-7-1 in 2011.
- Standards on information models and ontology with
 - the on-going development of a guide and plan to develop smart energy ontologies (IEC 63417),
 - the publication of core data models in the power utility domain, e.g., IEC 61850-7-2, and IEC 61850-7-3 and 7-4 for substations in 2010, with extensions to distributed energy resources with the IEC 61850-7-420 in 2021, to hydro power plants with IEC 61850-7-410 in 2012 or to wind farms IEC 61400-25 in 2016, and many other domains to come through transitional namespaces in the IEC 61850-90 series (Power quality, Condition maintenance and sensor network, Flexible alternate current transmission systems),
 - the publication of the common data dictionary, e.g., IEC 61360-1 in 2017, IEC 61360-4 on-line or IEC 61360-7 in 2024,
 - the publication of CIM or common information model, e.g., IEC 61970-1 and IEC 61970-2 in 2005, IEC 61970-301-v7 in 2020, IEC 61970-302-v2 in 2024, IEC 61970-401 in 2022, IEC 61970-600-1 in 2021, IEC 61970-552 in 2016, IEC 61968-1 in 2020,
 - the publication of CGMES or common grid model exchanged standard, with IEC 61970-600-1 in 2021,

⁶ <https://iec61850.dvl.iec.ch/>

- the publication of IRM or interface reference model, with IEC 61968-1 in 2020, and extensions for distribution with ISO 61968-11 in 2013
- Standards on interoperability profiles with the publication of power systems profiles, e.g., IEC 61850-7-7 in 2018, IEC 61968-13 in 2021, 61968-100 in 2022, 62361-103 in 2018)

Mentioned energy standards are showed in Table 5. Note that these standards are often the outcome of other initiatives such as the utility communication architecture (UCA) in 1998. A resulting CIM users group was formed in 2005 and its equivalent for IEC 61850 in 2005 as well. The CIM users group provides today a forum in stakeholder cooperate and leverage the IEC CIM international standards⁷ while the IEC 61850 users groups is very active in supporting interoperability and conformance testing of IEC 61850 implementations.

Table 5 – Examples of energy standards (IEC SyC Smart energy, IEC TC57 and others)

Category	Title	Id	Data	URL	
Architecture and interoperability framework	CEN-CENELEC-ETSI Smart Grid Coordination Group Smart Grid Reference Architecture	SGAM	2012	https://www.cencenelec.eu/media/CEN-CENELEC/AreasOfWork/CEN-CENELEC_Topics/Smart%20Grids%20and%20Meters/Smart%20Grids/reference_architecture_smartgrids.pdf	
	Power Utility Reference architecture	IEC 62357-1	2016	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/26251	
	Definition of extended SGAM smart energy grid reference architecture model	IEC SRD 63200	2021	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/62757	
	Guide and plan to develop Smart energy Ontologies	IEC 63417	Under development	https://www.iec.ch/dyn/www/?p=103:38:5009880199818:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_AP_EX_PAGE,FSP_PROJECT_ID:11825,23,105467	
Interoperability	Communication networks and systems for power utility automation	Introduction and overview	IEC TR 61850-1	2013	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/6007
		Communication requirements for functions and device models	IEC 61850-5	2013	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/6012
		Basic communication structure - Principles and models	IEC 61850-7-1	2011	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/6014
Information Model and ontology	Communication networks and systems for power utility automation	Basic information and communication structure - Abstract communication service interface (ACSI)	IEC 61850-7-2	2010	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/66525
		Basic communication structure - Common data classes	IEC 61850-7-3	2010	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/6016
		Basic communication structure - Compatible logical node classes and data object classes	IEC 61850-7-4	2010	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/6017
		Basic communication structure - Hydroelectric power plants - Communication for monitoring and control	IEC 61850-7-410	2012	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/23693
		Basic communication structure - Distributed energy resources and distribution automation logical nodes	IEC 61850-7-420	2021	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/34384
		Configuration description language for communication in power utility automation systems related to IEDs	IEC 61850-6	2009	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/63319
		Transitional namespaces for new domains (condition maintenance, sensor network, FACTs, power quality, microgrids, thermal energy...)	IEC TR 61850-90 series	Transitional	https://products.iec.ch/home

⁷ See <https://cimug.ucaiug.org/>

	Standard data element types with associated classification scheme	Definitions - Principles and methods	IEC 61360-1	2017	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/28560	
		Common data dictionary	IEC 61360-4	On line	https://cdd.iec.ch/	
		Data dictionary of cross-domain concepts	IEC 61360-7	2024	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/72956	
	Energy management system application program interface (EMS-API)		Guidelines and general requirements	EC 61970-1	2005	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/6208
			Glossary	EC 61970-2	2005	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/6209
			Common information model (CIM) base	IEC 61970-301 v7	2020	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/62698
			Common information model (CIM) dynamics	IEC 61970-302 v2	2024	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/68152
			Profile framework	IEC 61970-401	2022	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/62719
			CIMXML Model exchange format	IEC 61970-552	2016	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/25939
			Common Grid Model Exchange Standard (CGMES) - Structure and rules	IEC 61970-600-1	2021	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/63866
			Application integration at electric utilities - System interfaces for distribution management	Interface architecture and general recommendations	IEC 61968-1	2020
Common information model (CIM) extensions for distribution	IEC 61968-11	2013	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/6199			
Interoperability profiles	Communication networks and systems for power utility automation	Guideline for definition of Basic Application Profiles (BAPs) using IEC 61850	IEC TR 61850-7-6	2019	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/62972	
		Machine-processable format of IEC 61850-related data models for tools	IEC TR 61850-7-7	2018	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/29018	
	Application integration at electric utilities - System interfaces for distribution management	Common distribution power system model profiles	IEC 61968-13	2021	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/34213	
		IEC implementation profiles for application integration	IEC 61968-100	2022	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/67766	
	Power systems management and associated information exchange - Interoperability in the long term	Standard profiling	IEC TR 62361-103	2018	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/61296	
	Security profiles	Power systems management and associated information exchange - Data and communications security	IEC 62351 series	2007	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/6912	

2.3 Conformity Assessment Standards

Conformity assessment activities aim to provide confidence in an object of conformity. There can be different objectives:

- Compliance with a standard. From this perspective, *conformity assessment* focuses on verifying that requirements specified in a standard are met. This is supervised by CASCO⁸, the ISO committee that develops policy guidance and publishes standards on conformity assessment. Many of CASCO published documents are common to ISO and IEC. CASCO provides strict rules on the principle of separation between requirements to be evaluated, and requirements of the evaluation process itself⁹. They apply for instance on management systems standards such as ISO/IEC 27001 on information security in 2005, ISO/IEC 27701 on privacy information in

⁸ <https://www.iso.org/fr/casco.html>

⁹ Reference may be made to clause 33 of part 2 of the ISO directives: <https://www.iso.org/sites/directives/current/part2/>

2019 with a new edition planned in 2025, or ISO/IEC 42001 on artificial intelligence.

- Interoperability assurance which focuses on verifying that requirements related to interoperability constraints are met. Examples in the health domain, are the implementation of terminological terms with ISO 12310 in 2015, HL7 v2 conformance methodology in 2020, HL7 v3 on constraints on messages in 2015, HL7 electronic health records profiles from 2015 onwards. Examples in energy from the power utility automation 61850 standards are IEC 61850-10 in 2012, IEC 62351-100-3 in 2020, IEC 62351-100-4 in 2023.

The examples of conformity related standards from ISO/IEC JTC1 (ICT), HL7 (health) or TC57 (Energy) are provided in table 6.

Table 6 – Examples of conformity related standards (ICT JTC1, Health HL7, Energy IEC TC57)

Category	Title		Date	URL	
ICT	Information security management systems — Requirements		ISO/IEC 27001	2005, 2013, 2022 https://www.iso.org/standard/27001	
	Extension to ISO/IEC 27001 and ISO/IEC 27002 for privacy information management — Requirements and guidelines		ISO/IEC 27701	2019 https://www.iso.org/standard/71670.html	
	Privacy information management systems — Requirements and guidance		ISO/IEC 27701 Ed2	2025 https://www.iso.org/standard/85819.html	
	Artificial intelligence — Management system		ISO/IEC 42001	2023 https://www.iso.org/standard/81230.html	
Health	Principles and guidelines for the measurement of conformance in the implementation of terminological systems		ISO/TR 12310	2015 https://www.iso.org/standard/51346.html	
	HL7 V2 Implementation Guide Quality Criteria, Release 1			2020 https://www.hl7.org/implement/standards/product_brief.cfm?product_id=608	
	HL7 Version 2 Conformance Methodology Release 1			2020 https://www.hl7.org/implement/standards/product_brief.cfm?product_id=533	
	HL7 Version 3 Standard: Refinement, Constraint, and Localization (RCL) to V3 Messages, R2			2015 https://www.hl7.org/implement/standards/product_brief.cfm?product_id=76	
	HL7 Electronic Health Records profile standards https://www.hl7.org/implement/standards/product_section.cfm?section=11	EHR Behavioral Health Functional Profile, Release 1			2014, 2024 https://www.hl7.org/implement/standards/product_brief.cfm?product_id=14
		EHR System Long Term Care Functional Profile, Release 1 - US Realm			2015 https://www.hl7.org/implement/standards/product_brief.cfm?product_id=134
		EHR System Problem-Oriented Health Record (POHR) Functional Profile, Release 1			2023 https://www.hl7.org/implement/standards/product_brief.cfm?product_id=630
		EHR-S FM R2.1 Functional Profile: Problem-Oriented Health Record (POHR) for Problem List Management (PLM), Edition 1			2023 https://www.hl7.org/implement/standards/product_brief.cfm?product_id=630
		EHR-S Functional Profile: Meaningful Use, Release 1 - US Realm			2015 EHR-S Functional Profile: Meaningful Use, Release 1 - US Realm
		EHR-System Public Health Functional Profile, Release 2			2015 https://www.hl7.org/implement/standards/product_brief.cfm?product_id=278
		EHRS-FM R2.0.1: Usability Functional Profile, Release 1			2022 https://www.hl7.org/implement/standards/product_brief.cfm?product_id=611
		EHRS-FM Release 2 Functional Profile: 2015 Meaningful Use, Release 1 – US Realm			2020 https://www.hl7.org/implement/standards/product_brief.cfm?product_id=474
		EHRS-FM Release 2: Immunization Functional Profile, Release 1			2020 https://www.hl7.org/implement/standards/product_brief.cfm?product_id=521
Electronic Health Record System Functional Model (EHR-S FM) Release 2.1			2020 Electronic Health Record System Functional Model (EHR-S FM) Release 2.1		
Energy	Communication networks and systems for power utility automation	Conformance testing	IEC 61850-10	2012 https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/6008	
	Power systems management and associated information exchange Data and communication security	Conformance test cases for the IEC 62351-3, the secure communication extension for profiles including TCP/IP	IEC 62351-100-3	2020 https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/61597	
		Cybersecurity conformance testing for IEC 62351-4	IEC 62351-100-4	2023 https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/63323	

3 The Changing Context

3.1 Ecosystems or Socio-technical Systems

The term ecosystem is used to characterize an infrastructure and associated services based on a community of organizations and stakeholders. The term can be used for smart cities, but in also in application domains (e.g., transport, energy, health, metaverse) or technology domains (e.g., AI, IoT, digital twin, distributed ledger technology), or activity domain (e.g., conformance, regulation).

Ecosystems are becoming increasingly complex due to the number of organizations and stakeholders involved, the diversity of their roles, and the diversity of technologies (artificial intelligence, digital twins or virtual worlds). Standardization accompanies this development in the following way:

- standards on **systems of systems engineering**, e.g., with ISO/IEC/IEEE 21841 on a taxonomy of systems of systems, ISO/IEC/IEEE 21839 on the impact of systems of systems on the life cycle, or ISO/IEC/IEEE 21840 on the use for systems of systems of ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288 (reference standard on system life cycle processes).
- standards on **smart cities**, e.g., with the ISO/IEC 30145 series on a reference framework in smart cities, the 5087 series on city data models, or ISO/IEC 27570 on privacy guidelines for smart cities.
- standards on **trustworthiness**, e.g., with ISO/IEC 5723 on vocabulary, ISO/IEC 31303 on an overview and concepts, ISO/IEC 30149 on the principles of trust for the Internet of Things, or ISO/IEC 30147 on the integration of trustworthiness activities in the lifecycle of an IoT system, based on the ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288 standard.
- standards on **governance**, e.g., with ISO/IEC 38500 on information technology governance, ISO/IEC 38501-1 on data governance, ISO/IEC 38507 on the impact of artificial intelligence, and ISO/IEC 38509 on responsible governance for social inclusion.

The listed standard examples are showed in table 7.

Table 7 – Examples of ecosystem related standards

Category	Title		Date	URL		
System of systems engineering	Taxonomy of systems of systems		ISO/IEC/IEEE 21841:2019	2019	https://www.iso.org/standard/71957.html	
	System of systems (SoS) considerations in life cycle stages of a system		ISO/IEC/IEEE 21839	2019	https://www.iso.org/standard/71955.html	
	Guidelines for the utilization of ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288 in the context of system of systems (SoS)		ISO/IEC/IEEE 21840	2019	https://www.iso.org/standard/71956.html	
Smart cities	Smart City ICT reference framework	Smart city business process framework	ISO/IEC 30145-1	2021	https://www.iso.org/standard/76371.html	
		Smart city knowledge management framework	ISO/IEC 30145-2	2020	https://www.iso.org/standard/76372.html	
		Smart city engineering framework	ISO/IEC 30145-3	2020	https://www.iso.org/standard/76373.html	
	City data model	Foundational level concepts		ISO/IEC 5087-1	2023	https://www.iso.org/standard/80718.html
		City level concepts		ISO/IEC 5087-2	2024	https://www.iso.org/standard/80742.htm
		Service level concepts	Transportation planning	ISO/IEC 5087-4	Development	https://www.iso.org/standard/80744.html
			Public health emergencies	ISO/IEC 5087-4	Development	https://www.iso.org/standard/89870.html
Privacy protection — Privacy guidelines for smart cities		ISO/IEC 27570	2021	https://www.iso.org/standard/71678.html		
Trustworthiness	Vocabulary		ISO/IEC 5723	2022	https://www.iso.org/standard/81608.html	
	Overview and concepts		ISO/IEC 31303	Development	https://www.iso.org/standard/88510.html	
	Internet of things — Methodology for trustworthiness of IoT system/service		ISO/IEC 30147	2021	https://www.iso.org/standard/53267.html	
	Internet of Things (IoT) — Trustworthiness principle		ISO/IEC 30149	2024	https://www.iso.org/standard/53269.html	

Governance	Governance of IT for the organization		ISO/IEC 38500	2015, 2024	https://www.iso.org/standard/81684.html
	Governance of IT	Governance of data Part 1: Application of ISO/IEC 38500 to the governance of data	ISO/IEC 38501-1	2017	https://www.iso.org/standard/56639.html
		Governance implications of the use of artificial intelligence by organizations	ISO/IEC 38507	2022	https://www.iso.org/standard/56641.html
		Responsible governance for social inclusion	ISO/IEC 38509	Development	https://www.iso.org/standard/89911.html

3.2 Policies and Regulations

Regulation influences standardization, particularly in Europe with the concept of *harmonized standards*, which are developed by a European Standardization Organisations (CEN, CENELEC or ETSI)¹⁰, following a request from the European Commission concerning an union legislation. Manufacturers, other economic operators or conformity assessment bodies use these harmonized standards to demonstrate that products, services or processes comply with this legislation. Table 8 below lists examples of harmonized standard requests made by the European commission.

Table 8 – Examples of recent standardisation requests in Europe

European Union regulation			European Commission standardisation request		
Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 on Artificial Intelligence (AI Act)	2021-04 2024-07	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L_202401689	Draft standardisation request to the European Standardisation Organisations in support of safe and trustworthy artificial intelligence	2022-12	https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/52376
Proposal for regulation on horizontal cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements	2022-09 -	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52022PC0454	Draft standardisation request to European Standards Organisations in support of Union policy on cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements	2024-04	https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/58974
Regulation (EU) 2023/1542 on batteries and waste batteries	2023-07	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:3A32023R1542	Draft standardisation request as regards digital product passports	2023-10	https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/56175

3.3 Interoperability Frameworks

Interoperability processes are facilitated by the use of interoperability frameworks, which provide rules and recommendations to stakeholders involved in the process. Examples for work of frameworks are the following:

- NIST has worked on several interoperability programs in various application domains:
 - on energy, the NIST smart grid group published in 2020 a NIST framework and roadmap of smart grid interoperability standards, release 4.0¹¹.
 - on health, the NIST systems interoperability group is supporting the use of standards and the development of testing infrastructure for healthcare¹²
 - on public safety, the NIST public safety communications research division has provided a report on the interoperability of real-time public safety data¹³, and

¹⁰ <https://www.cencenelec.eu/about-cen/>, <https://www.cencenelec.eu/about-cenelec/>, <https://www.etsi.org/>

¹¹

<https://www.nist.gov/system/files/documents/2020/07/24/Smart%20Grid%20Draft%20Framework.pdf>

¹² <https://www.nist.gov/itl/products-and-services/healthcare-standards-testing>

¹³ https://www.nist.gov/system/files/documents/2019/06/27/nist.ir_.8255.pdf

- on voting system, the NIST information technology and voting systems group has provided support on common data formats in an election eco-system¹⁴
- The European interoperability framework was published in 2010 to address the interoperability of public services across member states of the European Union. A subsequent version was provided in 2017, covering three parts:
 - principles:
 - subsidiarity and proportionality,
 - openness,
 - transparency,
 - reusability,
 - technology neutrality and data portability,
 - user centricity,
 - inclusion and accessibility,
 - security and privacy,
 - multilingualism,
 - administrative simplification,
 - preservation of information,
 - assessment of effectiveness and efficiency;
 - interoperability layers:
 - legal,
 - organisation,
 - semantic,
 - technical; and
 - a conceptual model in integrated public services provision including the following components:
 - integrated service delivery,
 - coordination function,
 - reuse of data and services,
 - catalogues describing reusable services and other assets,
 - integrated public service governance,
 - security and privacy.

In parallel an eHealth interoperability framework was published in 2012.

- In Europe as well, the CEN-CENELEC-ETSI Smart Grid co-ordination group created an interoperability framework and associated method to apply in the context of the electric energy, to reach interoperability (SGAM) – This has been further promoted and extended in IEC through 2 main publications :
 - The IEC SRD 63200 transposed the SGAM into digital artefacts (IEC 63200 ontology) and extended to the interface with other energies (thermal, gaz)
 - The IEC 62559 series formalized the use cases methodology as a corner stone of the interoperability framework. This series also includes standardized information exchange models to facilitate the exchange of use cases between engineering tools. To extend its scope of application, and increase its awareness, this IEC 62559 series is currently being transposed into a future IEC Guide 125.

Table 9 – Examples of interoperability frameworks

Initiative	Date	URL
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¹⁴ <https://www.nist.gov/itl/voting/interoperability>

NIST	Framework for Smart grids	2020	https://www.nist.gov/ct/smart-connected-systems-division/smart-grid-group/smart-grid-framework
	Systems interoperability group for healthcare		https://www.nist.gov/itl/products-and-services/healthcare-standards-testing
	Interoperability of real-time public safety data		https://www.nist.gov/system/files/documents/2019/06/27/nist.ir_8255.pdf
	Information technology and voting systems		https://www.nist.gov/itl/voting/interoperability
European union	European Interoperability Framework	2010	https://web.archive.org/web/20160304233755/http://ec.europa.eu/isa/documents/isa_annex_ii_eif_en.pdf
	The New European Interoperability Framework	2017	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52022PC0454 https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:2c2f2554-0faf-11e7-8a35-01aa75ed71a1.0017.02/DOC_3&format=PDF
	eHealth European Interoperability Framework	2012	https://publications.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/3c5cc69d-7f06-42ab-bdfe-ed82307a8e2/language-en/format-PDF/source-52308887
CEN-CENELEC-ETSI	Smart Grid interoperability framework (SGAM) with its first set of standards and associated methods	2012-2016	https://www.cenelec.eu/areas-of-work/cen-cenelec-topics/smart-grids-and-meters/smart-grids/
IEC	IEC SRD 63200 extended Smart Grid interoperability framework	2019	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/62757
	IEC TR 63097 Smart Grid roadmap	2017	https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/27785
	IEC 62559 series : use cases methodology	2015	https://webstore.iec.ch/

4 Evolution of Standardisation Practice for Interoperability

4.1 Interoperability of Standards

International standardization must work on two challenges.

- The first challenge is to establish a standardization practice to build, produce and publish information models, meeting specific requirements associated to such digital content, i.e.
 - Incremental Agility, time to market, maintenance, user feedbacks
 - Technical governance
 - Favoring the re-use of existing
 - Tooling (digital open collaboration platform)
 - Cross entity governance (breaking the silos – ensuring modelling occurs the closest to where the knowledge is)
 - Distribution (multi format (XML, RDF, OWL, XMI, paper, web, ...), (free) access, trustworthiness)
 - Translation (each country may need to get the information model in its own set of human languages)
 - Profiling (standards or even specific to given groups of users)
- The second challenge is the establishment of a practice of standard construction that enables the use of cross-cutting standards in vertical domains. To make it happen, this practice will require significant work in the coordination process between standardization committees on information models. Figure 1 shows examples of information models on
 - Horizontal technologies (e.g., artificial intelligence, virtual worlds, IoT, digital twins, DLT, quantum).
 - Cross-cutting characteristics (e.g., security, privacy, resilience, safety of sustainability),
 - Applications (e.g., health, energy, transport, manufacturing, finance),
 - Ecosystems (e.g., smart cities, conformity)

Figure 1 – Examples of Information models

4.2 Interoperability of Concepts and Architectures

International standardization must work on two challenges.

- The first challenge is to align the work on concept standards to ensure interoperability of concepts. Standards on concepts and information models can be defined by multiple committees. Coordination on their development and governance will have to be enhanced. The following standards can be mentioned for development,
 - ISO 704 (Terminology work — Principles and methods),
 - ISO 1087-1 (Terminology work — Vocabulary Part 1: Theory and application),
 - this is complemented by guides, such as the ISO/IEC Guide 77 serie (Guide for specification of product properties and classes)
- The second challenge is to align the work on architecture standards to ensure interoperability of architectures. Standards on architecture can be defined by multiple committees. Coordination on their development will have to be enhanced. The following standards can be mentioned:
 - ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010 (architecture description),
 - ISO/IEC/IEEE 42020 (architecture process),
 - ISO/IEC/IEEE 42030 (architecture evaluation),
 - ISO/IEC/IEEE 42024 (architecture fundamentals),
 - ISO/IEC/IEEE 42042 (reference architecture),
 - ISO/IEC 40141 (guidelines on reference architectures),
 - ISO/IEC 30141 (IoT reference architecture).

Table 10 lists the examples of concept and architecture standards.

Table 10 – Examples of concept and architecture standards

Category	Title		Data	URL
Concept	Terminology work — Principles and methods		ISO 704	2009, 2020 https://www.iso.org/standard/79077.html
	Terminology work — Vocabulary Part 1: Theory and application		ISO 1087-1	2000, 2019 https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/en/#iso:std:iso:1087:ed-2:v1:en
	Guide for specification of product properties and classes	Fundamental benefits	ISO/IEC Guide 77-1	2008 https://www.iso.org/standard/44065.html
		Technical principles and guidance	ISO/IEC Guide 77-2	2008 https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/11954
Architecture	Software, systems and enterprise	Architecture description	ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010	2022 https://www.iso.org/standard/74393.html
		Architecture processes	ISO/IEC/IEEE 42020	2019 https://www.iso.org/standard/68982.html
		Architecture evaluation framework	ISO/IEC/IEEE 42030	2019 https://www.iso.org/standard/73436.html
	Enterprise, systems and software	Architecture fundamentals	ISO/IEC/IEEE 42024	Development https://www.iso.org/standard/87510.html
		Reference architectures	ISO/IEC/IEEE 42042	
	IoT reference architecture		ISO/IEC Ed2 30141	2024 https://www.iso.org/standard/88800.html
	Guidance on reference architecture		ISO/IEC 40141	Development https://www.iec.ch/ords/f?p=103:38:710954471973193:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_APEX_PAGE,FSP_PROJECT_ID:20486,23,126453

4.3 Interoperability of Systems

The changing context as explained above requires a more flexible and agile publication of interoperability profile standards to enabling the interoperability of systems. As showed in Figure 1, the interoperability of systems will benefit from a standardisation practice that is based on the following capabilities:

- Interoperability of standards, through the SMART approach.

- Interoperability of concepts and architectures.

Figure 2 – Roadmap on the evolution of standards

International standardization must work on two challenges.

- The first challenge is to ensure assurance and conformity assessment, when interoperability profile standards can involve elements defined by multiple instances.
- The second challenge is to enable the use and publication of standards involving multiple standard development organisations (SDO). This can be enabled technically through SMART standards but it requires copyright and business agreements.

5 Conclusion: Towards a New Ecosystem of Standardisation Practice

SDOs must engage in a standardisation practice to enable standard, concept and architecture and systems interoperability.

We have listed the following challenges:

- Adapt the standardization ecosystem practice to build, publish and maintain information models, which breaks silos, improve consistency and facilitates the life of users.
- Establishment of standard construction that enables the use of cross-cutting standards in vertical domains.
- Align the work on concept standards to ensure interoperability of concepts.
- Align the work on architecture standards to ensure interoperability of architectures.
- Ensure assurance and conformity assessment, when interoperability profile standards can involve elements defined by multiple instances.
- Enable the use and publication of standards involving multiple SDOs

IEC SMB/SG12 has published a document¹⁵ which points out the “absence of a standardized method for transposing information into digital artifacts”. It uses the term semantic domains which we can associate here with information models and lists the following needs

- Assessment on when an information model has to be created.
- Agility and time-to-market.
- Tooling.
- Favouring re-use across multiple SDOs.
- Information model governance
- Distribution and translation

Appropriately addressing these needs will enable (1) the advent of digital twin applications, and (2) the agility needed for the metaverse.

¹⁵ July 2024. <https://iec.ch/basecamp/semantic-interoperability-what-it-why-it-important-and-what-needs-be-done-standardization>

